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PROFESSIONAL FULLFILLMENT AMONG INDIAN RAILWAY EMPLOYEES WITH REFERENCE TO SOUTH CENTRAL RAILWAY (SCR).

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation focuses on the professional fulfillment of railway employees in India. This study focused on professional fulfillment, and the railway department took various measures toward subordinates, helpfulness, and the ability to withstand job stress, among other things. With the help of this bonding, the level of professional fulfillment will be increased, and it has given good results in railways. Group and organizational dynamics have a significant impact on professional happiness.

Keywords: Professional fulfillment, Satisfaction, IR, SCR

INTRODUCTION

Different researchers or philosophers derive and assess job satisfaction in different ways. It alludes to a positive sense of goal-setting at work being achieved. However, occupational fulfillment is more important than individual happiness, contentment, and pleasure with oneself. In general, it may be assumed that low motivation at work is a possible result of employee job unhappiness. Today, academics frequently study job satisfaction in order to better understand the aspects that contribute to the process of choosing a comfortable life and receiving happiness from it. For all people in all civilizations, satisfaction is the most likable and desired quality. Today, social scientists, behavioral scientists, and management scientists are all interested in the research of work happiness. Regardless of the type of work they do, all employees tend to improve the workplace by utilizing their opportunities, opportunities, and talents. Every work environment would give an employee the chance to develop new social bonds with coworkers, managers, and other individuals. Additionally, having a job will undoubtedly assist with bad financial situations, taking on duties, and future planning. Therefore, an employee wants to feel positively about learning new skills or upgrading existing ones, forming better social connections, enhancing their financial situation, and making better career plans. Such occurrences might be viewed as a step in the direction of obtaining occupational satisfaction. Additionally, work satisfaction is considered to be a key indication of overall personal wellbeing as well as a very effective predictor of an employee's intents or decisions to quit a job. Additionally important in daily living is work satisfaction. As a result, both employers and workers are very concerned about employee pleasure at work. A range of factors impact job happiness, including pay, development possibilities, coworkers, supervision, workload, appreciation, the office climate, and structure and management. Poor working circumstances, overwork, low pay, little chance for advancement or promotion, and a lack of recognition must all be addressed right once to prevent the worst results, such as loss of motivation, indifference, dissatisfaction, poor productivity, absenteeism, and even high turnover rates. As a result, job happiness is growing crucial in the workplace. Employers have come to understand that the more "successful and satisfied" their workers feel at work, the more motivated they are, and the better they perform. In every line of employment, the workplace has a substantial influence on job satisfaction. When workers are unhappy with their occupations, they typically display little interest in them, which has a detrimental effect on corporate performance.

IMPLICATIONS

To assess the overall status of employee morale, researchers and practitioners are frequently interested in investigating global job satisfaction. Examining aspect circumstances is seen to be helpful for developing a critical knowledge of employee satisfaction, nevertheless. Consequently, job satisfaction may be categorized as either facet or overall satisfaction.

REVIEWS

Vaddi.Ramesh, Dr.Ashok Kumar Katta (2023), fascinated by the contentment of the Guntakal Railway Division's employees. The majority of the company's employees are happy with the results. It's safe to assume that the majority of individuals are aware of and trust the company's strategy. Most employees are rewarded for their efforts. Railroads that compensate their employees well will survive. Workers in a corporation should work together in the same way as members of a family work together to achieve a common goal. Every day, people are given the opportunity to showcase their skills and get recognition. The highest echelons of government are easily accessible.

Vaddi.Ramesh, Dr.Ashok Kumar Katta (2022), It is the sum of all factors that have a significant impact on an individual's capacity to do any given task and their honest output that leads to job satisfaction. Job pride elements emerge and grow both outside (uncontrollable) and inwardly (controllable) in the working individual's environment. Employment pride is the sum of all physiological, psychological, and conditional factors that either please or dissatisfy a worker with his or her employment. Job pride findings have ramifications for assessing, thinking, doing, and feeling. The purpose of this study is to investigate various aspects of job satisfaction, challenges, and remedial methods affecting railway staff operating in the Guntakal Division of the Indian Railways' South Central Railway Division. Indian Railways' Guntakal Division.

Vaddi.Ramesh, Dr.Ashok Kumar Katta (2022), There are several factors that contribute to an individual's ability to accomplish any given job and their true output. External and internal factors contribute to job satisfaction, which can also be impacted by the working individual's surroundings. True, job pride may have both positive and negative consequences for the individual, the company, and the country. We look at a variety of physiological, psychological, and environmental factors to determine if a person is happy with his or her job. Job satisfaction has emotional, cognitive, behavioral, and evaluative consequences. The primary purpose of this research is to determine how a variety of work pleasure components and obstacles affect railway personnel on the Guntakal Railway.

Ashok Kumar and Bala Nageswara Rao, (2015) According to the argument, Indian railroads are the most costly in terms of human resources and staff costs (workers on rolls + pension). Employees use more than 61% of overall operating expenses.

Aswathappa K (2010) in his book "Organizational Behavior" as "the general attitude of employees toward their jobs." According to him, work satisfaction arises when a person has a favorable attitude toward his or her job. When the attitude is negative, there is dissatisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

Objectives:

- To find out the unbiasedness towards their subordinates in IR authorities to promote employee work satisfaction.
- To study IR supervisors are kind and helpful for the subordinates.
- To Analyze Employees in IR have the ability to withstand job stress

Scope

The current study aims to examine the degree of work satisfaction among Indian railway personnel. The current study's scope is both broad and limited. The study's scope is also considered limited because it only covers one of India's 7,146 railway stations.

DATA COLLECTION AND SAMPLE

This study is based on the collecting of primary and secondary data. It is descriptive, comparative, and analytical. In the current study, descriptive analysis was carried out while keeping the study’s requirements in mind. A comparison of numerous factors is performed to determine work satisfaction in the transportation and commercial divisions. The analytical section discusses the issues that contribute to job unhappiness and the need to improve job satisfaction in the transportation and commercial departments. The study identified many characteristics that determine work satisfaction by nature. In this study, a questionnaire, an interview, and an observation approach were employed. Sample size 276.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table – 1 Supervisors are unbiased towards their subordinates

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Transport department employees	Commercial department employees	Total
1	V Almost always true	(29.57%) 34	(32.30%) 52	(31.16%) 86
2	V Mostly true	(47.83%) 55	(43.48%) 70	(45.29%) 125
3	V Sometimes true	(22.61%) 26	(24.22%) 39	(23.55%) 65
4	V Rarely true	-	-	-
5	V Not at all true	-	-	-
Total		(100%) 115	(100%) 161	(100%) 276
Mean average		4.07	4.08	4.08
F-test values		F value-1.511429	T value-7.71	

Source: Primary data

Note: V indicates vertical percentage to the total

The opinions of sample respondents on the statement “Supervisors are unbiased towards their subordinates” are shown in Table 1. The majority of the total sample respondents, 45.29 percent, believed the statement was mostly accurate. Those who follow it and who account for 31.16 percent felt the statement-almost always true. The remaining sample employees who constitute 23.55 percent felt the statement-sometimes true.

Mean Result: The overall weighted average mean score stands at 4.08.

An examination of the views of personnel in the transport and commercial departments indicates the following: Among the employees of transport department, majority of them who accounts for 47.83 percent felt the statement-mostly true. Those who follow it and who account for 29.57 percent felt the statement-almost always true. The remaining sample employees who constitute 22.61 percent felt the statement-sometimes true.

Mean Result: The weighted average mean score of this department stands at 4.07. The commercial department sample respondents indicated more or less identical sentiments, with minimal difference in percentages. The weighted average mean score of this department stands at 4.08. From the above analysis, it can be concluded that superiors are unbiased towards their subordinates.

Mean Result: It is reinforced by the overall weighted average mean score of 4.08.

F-TEST

The data is also checked using statistical values. The F-test was performed in this respect, and the results reveal that the computed F value is 1.511429, while the table value at (1,4) degrees of freedom and at 5% level of significance is 7.71. Because the estimated F value is smaller than the table value, it is possible to conclude that there is no significant difference between the mean replies of employees in the transport and commercial departments. To summarize, supervisors are objective toward their subordinates.

Table – 2 IR supervisors are kind and helpful.

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Transport department employees	Commercial department employees	Total
1	V Almost always true	(52.17%) 60	(37.27%) 60	(43.48%) 120
2	V Mostly true	(30.43%) 35	(48.45%) 78	(40.94%) 113
3	V Sometimes true	(17.39%) 20	(14.29%) 23	(15.58%) 43
4	V Rarely true	-	-	-
5	V Not at all true	-	-	-
Total		(100%) 115	(100%) 161	(100%) 276
Mean average		4.35	4.23	4.28
F-test values		F value-0.590402	T value-7.71	

Source: Primary data

Note: V indicates vertical percentage to the total

The opinions of sample responders on the statement “Supervisors in IR are considerate and helpful” are shown in Table 2. The majority of the total sample respondents (43.48 percent) believed the statement-almost always true. Those who follow it and who account for 40.94 percent felt the statement-mostly true. The remaining sample employees who constitute 15.58 percent felt the statement-sometimes true.

Mean Result: The overall weighted average mean score stands at 4.28.

An examination of the views of personnel in the transport and commercial departments indicates the following: Among the sample respondents of transport department, majority of them who accounts for 52.17 percent felt the statement-almost always true. Those who follow it and who account for 30.43 percent felt the statement-mostly true. The remaining sample respondents who constitute 17.39 percent felt the statement-sometimes true.

Mean Result: The weighted average mean score of this department stands at 4.35.

Among the sample respondents of commercial department, majority of them who accounts for 48.45 percent felt the statement-mostly true. Those who follow it and who account for 37.27 percent felt the statement-almost always true. The remaining

sample respondents who constitute 14.29 percent felt the statement-sometimes true. The weighted average mean score of this department stands at 4.23. From the above analysis, it can be concluded that supervisors in IR are considerate and helpful.

Mean Result: The overall weighted average mean score of 4.28 supports the observation.

F-TEST

The data is also checked using statistical values. The F-test was performed in this respect, and the results reveal that the computed F value is at 0.590402, while the table value at (1,4) degrees of freedom and at 5% level of significance is at 7.71. Because the estimated F value is smaller than the table value, it is possible to conclude that there is no significant difference between the mean replies of employees in the transport and commercial departments. It demonstrates that managers are kind and helpful. The analysis is also shown graphically.

Table – 3 Employees in IR have the ability to withstand job stress

Sl. No.	Choice of response	Transport department employees	Commercial department employees	Total
1	V Almost always true	(17.39%) 20	(18.01%) 29	(17.75%) 49
2	V Mostly true	(18.26%) 21	(16.15%) 26	(17.03%) 47
3	V Sometimes true	(23.48%) 27	(19.88%) 32	(21.38%) 59
4	V Rarely true	(21.74%) 25	(24.22%) 39	(23.19%) 64
5	V Not at all true	(19.13%) 22	(21.74%) 35	(20.65%) 57
Total		(100%) 115	(100%) 161	(100%) 276
Mean average		2.93	2.84	2.88
F-test values		F val- ue-12.37427	T value-5.32	

Source: Primary data

Note: V indicates vertical percentage to the total

Table-3 summarizes survey respondents’ perspectives on the statement “IR employees have the ability to withstand job stress.” The majority of the entire sample respondents (23.19 percent) agreed with the statement-rarely true. Those who follow it and who account for 21.38 percent felt the statement-sometimes true. In the remaining sample, people who felt the statement-not at all true are relatively more than those who felt the statement-almost always true and mostly true.

Mean Result: The overall weighted average mean score stands at 2.88.

An examination of the views of personnel in the transport and commercial departments indicates the following. The majority of transport department sample respondents (23.48 percent) believed the statement-sometimes accurate. Those who follow it and who account for 21.74 percent felt the statement-rarely true. In the remaining sample, people who felt the statement-not at all true are relatively more than those who felt the statement-mostly true and almost always true. **Mean Result:** The weighted average mean score of this department stands at 2.93.

Among the employees of commercial department, majority of them who accounts for 24.22 percent felt the statement-rarely true. Those who follow it and who account for 21.74 percent felt the statement-not at all true. In the remaining

sample, people who felt the statement-sometimes true are relatively more than those who felt the statement-almost always true and mostly true. The weighted average mean score of this department stands at 2.84. From the above analysis, it can be concluded that employees in IR do not have the ability to withstand job stress.

Mean Result: It is reinforced by the overall weighted average mean score of 2.88.

F-TEST

The data is also checked using statistical values. The F-test was performed in this respect, and the results reveal that the computed F value is 12.37427, whereas the table value at (1,8) degrees of freedom and at 5% level of significance is 5.32. Because the computed F value is bigger than the table value, it is possible to deduce that there is a considerable difference between the mean replies of employees in the transport and commercial departments. It demonstrates that IR personnel lack the ability to resist occupational stress. The analysis is also shown graphically.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, by conducting research effectively, one can find the reasons for both job satisfaction and dissatisfaction, resulting in the promotion of determinants for the former while taking appeasement measures for the latter. It will also support the work organization to increase the levels of job satisfaction among the employees by taking into account such factors as grievance-handling procedures, employee recognition programs, and training programs. Job satisfaction impacts mainly on productivity, absenteeism, and turnover.

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

The author's examination of the acquired data using the F-test resulted in the provision of a study proposal's scope and recommendations.

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